

ENGAGE IOT

The background of the entire page is a photograph with a warm, orange-red color cast. On the left, a white power outlet is visible with a black two-pronged plug inserted. To the right, a black, rectangular IoT device with a handle and a small antenna is shown. The overall aesthetic is industrial and tech-oriented.

**SOCIETAL
ENGAGEMENTS
WITH THE
INTERNET
OF THINGS.**

A zine.

Key concepts

Internet of Things (IoT)

'An open and comprehensive network of intelligent objects that have the capacity to auto-organize, share information, data and resources, reacting and acting in face of situations and changes in the environment'[1]

Sociotechnical imaginaries

'collectively held, institutionally stabilized, and publicly performed visions of desirable futures, animated by shared understandings of forms of social life and social order attainable through, and supportive of, advances in science and technology'[2]

Social practice

'a routinized type of behaviour [...] [that] exists as a 'block' or 'a pattern which can be filled out by a multitude of single and often unique actions [...] consists of interdependencies between diverse elements including 'forms of bodily activities, forms of mental activities, "things" and their use, a background knowledge in the form of understanding, know-how, states of emotion and motivational knowledge''' [3]

What this is

In 2016 I became intrigued with a kind of technological devices being sold as smart and connected to the Internet. After years researching science and environmental topics, I wanted to try my hand at studying technology 'at the ground level', inside peoples' homes, as they go about their daily life.

A few years later, I managed to obtain funding to develop a research project on the Internet of Things (IoT) and gather together a small, all-female team of sociologists and anthropologists, some also working on STS, others on consumption and material culture.

We designed the project with two main layers: we wanted to examine both the 'macro level' of sociotechnical imaginaries around IoT (how it was represented by policy-makers, engineers, company managers, experts, consumer champions, law enforcers) and the 'micro level' of social practice (how connected devices were used in domestic settings). This is a situated research: we focused our attention in our country, Portugal, a small European country of limited means but an eager 'early adopter' of technology.

After two years of work, we have amassed a substantial volume of results that we are trying to process and analyse and discuss through various forms. Making a zine seemed a novel way of showing our findings and kick-starting a debate with diverse audiences.

Ana

What we did

A multi-layered research demanded a multi-methods approach. As such, in order to garner the sociotechnical imaginaries of IoT and reconstruct its ecosystem in Portugal, we performed content analysis of documents, media articles, and advertisements for products and we conducted 16 interviews with stakeholders (representatives from public agencies, companies, civil society organisations, higher education institutions and research centres).

Examining IoT practices at home was done through 21 interviews with families of users, visits to their homes, observation of the devices at work, photos and videos.

To tie all the loose ends, in the end we brought stakeholders and users together in a workshop, discussing the benefits and risks of IoT and how to enhance the former and mitigate the later.

Nurtured in the school of thought of public sociology, we did not want the results of our work confined to academic repositories, regardless of open access practices. For that, we created a dissemination strategy aimed at both academic and non-academic audiences, national and international. We experimented with new formats and also used tried and tested ones.

What we learned

The small IoT ecosystem in Portugal, made up of companies, government agencies, civil society organisations and higher education institutions, cannot be seen in isolation from the wider international/European context.

In 2022, 3 out of 10 Portuguese used IoT devices. Among these, smart TVs were the most prevalent, largely because new models typically include internet connectivity, making IoT a default feature. Slightly less than one in 10 respondents used smart home appliances, like robotic vacuum cleaners. IoT users in Portugal are mostly young, highly educated, affluent, and tech savvy.

Data Source: Eurostat, 2020 and 2022

Technologies for good?

With technological development, the rule has often been to invent first and ask later what the consequences can be. And as with other technologies, IoT has many affordances, but not fewer risks.

With the globalisation of markets, e-commerce and governments' fear that regulatory measures may hinder innovation, IoT devices are available to be bought with little to no control over security issues. Connected devices send an outflow of data and receive external inputs. The first is meant to improve performance but can be used to spy on the users (dataveillance [4]), for commercial (sell them more stuff, sell their data to third parties) or for law enforcement purposes. The latter offers all the convenience of control at a distance, but all the risks of denial of-service and cyber kinetic attacks.

Users are not unaware of the risks to their privacy, some take precautions such as changing passwords and using more secure routers, but others exhibit a sort of 'privacy resignation' [5], either because they don't believe they are important enough to be spied on and/or because they feel powerless to prevent it.

You
come to a point where you see things in perspective and you want things to work more than you want to know if your data is being searched. My data is probably already scattered all over the world and we'll never be safe from this. The moment we switch on, it's over, our privacy is over.

Amazon's Ring is the largest civilian surveillance network the US has ever seen
Lauren Bridges

'Smart' devices 'too dumb' to fend off cyber-attacks, say experts

Amazon gadget hijacks owner's heating after hearing radio report

Echo, a home automation gadget, reset its owner's thermostat after mistaking NPR broadcast on its capabilities for a voice command

CloudPets stuffed toys leak details of half a million users

Company's data compromised, leaking information including email addresses, passwords and voice recordings

It is undeniable that IoT can have extremely useful applications, such as in the efficient management of electricity grids, industrial processes, agricultural fields, and health systems. But being able to turn on the lights with a voice command, ask a smart speaker to tell a joke or check the contents of the fridge while sitting on the sofa might seem a somewhat futile use of technology (and one that only encourages further our sedentary lifestyle).

However, for people with disabilities, elderly or infirm, this technology can be the difference between staying in their own home, with some degree of autonomy or having to move into assisted living. For harassed parents, juggling work and child care, it can be time-saving, releasing them from dull chores of cooking and cleaning. For pet owners who work long hours away from home, it can be a way of checking up on their animal companions, give them treats and a bit of company.

Energy savings, energy waste

IoT devices are often sold on the promise of energy saving and efficiency. Anticipating users' needs and desires, they can turn on and shut off on their own, on a schedule or at the push of a button from anywhere in the world. Shutters that open at sunrise to make the most of the light, air conditioning that warms up the house just before owners arrive, smart lamps with sensors that are activated as someone passes by.

In truth, IoT devices are electricity gluttons, always on, requiring invisible infrastructure that has its own energy needs at home (routers, wi-fi extenders and boosters) and outside (service providers, data servers). The growing incorporation of AI in IoT devices will only worsen things, contributing to increased greenhouse gas emissions that are bringing us ever closer to global disaster [6].

IoT appliances, like all electronic devices, also need energy, water, plastic, rare earths and minerals for their manufacture, depleting already scarce resources. Some are easily broken or suffer malfunctions, all have built-in planned obsolescence, causing them to be often discarded and piled in the huge mountain of global e-waste.

And yet, some IoT devices do help users save energy. This is particularly true in houses with solar panels, which are also connected and provide real time information on energy generation. By using platforms like Home Assistant, an open source software (that sprung its own online communities), users can program appliances to make the most of cheap and abundant energy.

Again, these benefits can only be reaped by users who are affluent enough to buy the necessary equipment and tech savvy enough to manage it.

The solar panels also allow us to save money and understand when we can put the washing machines on; because after a month or two of using it, we have the energy production profile showing where we're spending the most, and the things we can change. And we've changed them.

The gender dimension

Many IoT products are designed and sold with the purpose of lightening the load of domestic work, Robot vacuum cleaners that Hoover the house by themselves, food processors that recommend recipes, fridges that alert the user when they are running out of milk, are all part of 'smart homes'.

From our interviews, we realised that in many families these appliances help rebalance in the gender distribution of domestic chores, when both members of the couple use the apps that control the devices.

However, we also observed instances where running these appliances remained the responsibility of women, whereas men were mostly in charge of the 'digital housekeeping' [7]: researching the products, buying them, setting them up and maintaining them.

I

check the app, but I'm more of a user. he's the one

who's always correcting, changing...

I sometimes go into the app and see some changes.... he's always at it, he

really likes it. We're even thinking about

him starting to do the installation

himself, because he has the time and

he really has this passion, he

likes it.

IoT objects are themselves gendered both by their makers and by their users. It is no coincidence that voice assistants commonly have female voices, reinforcing traditional views of women as subservient helpers. Users often name their robot vacuum cleaners, using mostly women's names. Furthermore, the design of IoT products and services, as well as the training of new computer engineers, remains largely a male-dominated sector. This bias is reflected in products primarily designed by men for men. One of the stakeholders we interviewed, a female lecturer, highlighted the importance of having women developing technological products and bringing their viewpoints to product design.

**we
believe that if we had the
women's perspective, the products
would be more suitable too. Because of user
experience. When we make a product, we have
to consider the user experience. And if there's a
woman developing that product, she's already
putting her point of view into it. Software seems
like a very technological thing, but it's a very
living thing.**

Where do we go from here

IoT is a fascinating object to observe the entanglements between technology and society, objects and humans, virtual and physical, data and infrastructure. Like most technologies, IoT tends to promise more than it delivers. It is costly and demanding in terms of expert know-how. Underwhelming performances and technical snags curtail its adoption. And it is fast being complemented or even replaced by the next technological fad (AI).

Making a zine about our research into IoT allowed us to zoom in and reflect on a handful of topics that piqued our attention. It endorsed us to use a freer format than traditional academic publications, combining text, photos, drawings, collages. It spurred a collaboration between sociology and design that we hadn't attempted before. It left us hungry for more interactions between research and creative endeavours.

Who we are

Ana Delicado is a sociologist, working in science and technology studies. She is a senior research fellow at ICS Universidade de Lisboa.

Jussara Rowland is a sociologist and postdoctoral researcher at ICS Universidade de Lisboa, focusing on participatory and creative methods, digital technologies, and science communication.

Clara Venâncio is a Design PhD student at the Faculty of Fine Arts, University of Porto, developing work at the crossroads of Design with Human-Animal Studies.

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